

CASE STUDY

The case study in Psychology: self-realization and personal growth from the subject's activity

El estudio de caso en Psicología: autorrealización y crecimiento personal desde la actividad del sujeto

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Abstract Personality is an essential psychological category that arises from the peculiar integration of bio-psycho-social components and how the subject faces the challenges of his environment since it is a key tool to understanding one's emotions and those of others. The case study in the context of personality psychology allowed a deep exploratory study of some primary psychological units and motivational psychological formations. For this purpose, various instruments were used, which involved the collection of detailed information about a person through multiple techniques, which, in this case, can be mentioned: projective instruments such as the 10-wishes test, the HTP, Rotter's sentence completion, as well as the Coopermish self-esteem inventory, and the Eysenck personality test, together with traditional methods of psychological research such as observation and interview. The present work's general objective is to study the configuration of a supposedly healthy subject's personality to describe the contents and functional aspects of the phonological dimension.

Keywords personality, case study, methods, primary psychological units, motivational psychological formations.

Resumen La personalidad es una importante categoría psicológica, que surge de la peculiar integración de los componentes bio-psico-sociales, y en cómo se enfrenta el sujeto a los desafíos de su entorno, ya que es una herramienta clave para comprender las propias emociones y las de los demás. El estudio de caso en el contexto de la psicología de la personalidad permitió un estudio exploratorio profundo de algunas unidades psicológicas primarias y de las formaciones psicológicas motivacionales. Para tal fin, se emplearon diversos instrumentos, que implicaron la recopilación de información minuciosa sobre una persona a través de diversas técnicas, que, en este caso se pueden mencionar: los instrumentos proyectivos como el test de los 10 deseos, el HTP, el completamiento de frases de Rotter, así como, el inventario de autoestima de Coopermish, y el test de personalidad de Eysenck. Conjuntamente de los métodos tradicionales de la investigación psicológica como lo son la observación y la entrevista. El presente trabajo tiene como objetivo general estudiar la configuración de la personalidad de un sujeto supuestamente sano, de modo que permita describirse los contenidos y aspectos funcionales que integran la dimensión persono-lógica.

Palabras clave personalidad, estudio de caso, métodos, unidades psicológicas primarias, formaciones psicológicas motivacionales.

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Introduction

Psychological knowledge is needed to interpret how a given subject behaves conveniently to study personality properly. Therefore, personality is seen as a configurational construct that belongs to an individual subject that manifests itself in a given context (activity), knowing that the personality traits of a subject “are not fixed,” as Allport (1937) expressed, quite rightly that “personality is the dynamic organization within the individual of those psycho-physical systems that determine their characteristic of adaptation to the environment” (p. 48), contributing to perfecting how the human being relates to others, also facilitating the existence of healthier and more effective interpersonal relationships.

Although a subject is unique and unrepeatable, he is built as a social being throughout his existence, based on the learning and experiences that the subject himself experiences; this was already proven by Vygotsky (1997) when he expressed that, “learning is a social process that contributes to the formation of personality” (p. 32). Therefore, the more experiences the subject has and participates with resilience in social life, the better formed the personality will be, and the more dynamic it will be; where will, coping, and responsibility must characterize people to achieve goals, from the actions and operations they undertake. Psychologist Angela Duckworth (2016) expressed it this way when she stated that “the development of personality is a journey that requires effort and commitment, not just talent” (p. 12).

In the research, some psychological tests and techniques were used to analyze and characterize the subject of study to determine the interrelations and modes of action. This allowed us to examine the subject’s life, experiences, and behaviors, which helped us better understand and describe his personality. In the development of the work, a brief conceptualization will be made about their use, feasibility, and functionality in the research configuration.

Based on the application and evaluation of the above, the following objectives are proposed as a guide for the research:

General objective: To study the personality configuration of a supposedly healthy subject. To describe the contents and

functional aspects that make up the personality of a supposedly healthy subject.

The objective was to examine the subject’s core psychological units and formations using various methods, tests, and techniques to assess personality as a structured and integrated whole. Additionally, it aims to identify recurring behavioral patterns in the subject’s personality.

Psychology scholars have defined personality in various ways, constantly integrating biological, psychological, and social factors. Table 1 highlights a review of classical and contemporary theories.

A central theme in these definitions is the integration of biological, social, and psychological elements, making each personality unique. Personality is a stable and complex organization of psychological functions, enabling self-regulation in key life areas and balancing affective and cognitive unity.

Following Vygotsky (1994b), personality is not solely an internal process but is shaped by social relationships. This study focuses on a case study of a supposedly healthy subject who voluntarily participated after providing informed consent. It will also describe, in general, the areas where the subject’s personality is expressed and developed.

Various research methods, tests, and techniques will be applied to achieve this, including observation, interviews, and psychological assessment tools. These tools include the 10 Wishes Technique, the Sentence Completion Test (Rotter), the HTP Test (House, Tree, Person), the Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory, and the Eysenck Personality Test. These tools will analyze personality and explore the subject’s personological configuration through multiple psychological evaluation sessions. These techniques’ methodological value and psychological significance in the case study will be further detailed.

Methodology

This case study applies various psychological research methods, techniques, and tests to describe and analyze the

Table 1. Theoretical perspectives in personality development

References	Personality development
Erikson (1950)	Develops through psychosocial stages
Horney (1950)	Results from the struggle between human needs and social pressures
Skinner (1953)	Formed through learned responses to the environment
Maslow (1954)	Driven by self-actualization and personal growth
Bandura (1977)	Influenced by behavior, personal factors, and environment
Vygotsky (1978, 1998)	Constructed through social interaction and cultural context
Goleman (1995)	Includes emotional intelligence as a key component
McCrae & Costa (1999)	Consists of stable psychological traits influencing behavior
Seligman (2002)	Understood through human strengths and life meaning

subject's behavior. These tools help assess personality, emotions, and interpersonal dynamics, providing valuable insights into human behavior.

Research methods include observation, which allows for a systematic analysis of behavior to identify emotional patterns and interpret interpersonal dynamics while minimizing biases (López, 2017; Brown, 2018; Gómez, 2020; Ruiz, 2022), and interviews, which facilitate an in-depth exploration of the subject's narratives, enhancing the understanding of their behavioral essence (Brown, 1999; Harris, 1999; Lewis, 1999).

Psychological Tests and Techniques:

10 Wishes Technique: Clarifies true desires, fostering resilience and intrinsic motivation (Seligman, 2011).

Sentence Completion Test: This test explores personality, emotions, and internal conflicts through indirect psychological analysis.

HTP Test (House, Tree, Person): This test assesses personality, self-concept, and social perceptions through drawings (Bender, 2003; Bellak, 1990).

Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory: This instrument evaluates self-esteem in various contexts, measuring perceived competence and worth (Coopersmith, 1967; Branden, 1994).

Eysenck Personality Test: Identifies personality traits based on extraversion-introversion, neuroticism, and psychoticism (McCrae & Costa, 2008).

These methods emphasize personality's dynamic nature, aligning with Allport's (1937) perspective that personality is "stable but not static." They contribute to self-awareness, identity formation, and psychological integration, demonstrating the continuous influence of experiences and learning.

Results and discussion

Psychological observation and interview are essential empirical methods for studying behaviors and reactions in the activity. During the first session, two essential methods for psychological research were used: "observation" and "interview." These methods can be used to obtain personal information necessary for the subject and the different areas in which his or her personality develops. It is important to note that the psychologist or observer must maintain an ethical approach while applying both methods to ensure the confidentiality and well-being of the subject under study.

Therefore, as Taylor (1999) specifies, "the combination of observation and interview in psychological research provides a complete view of the phenomenon studied" (p. 112). Thus, when observing, nuances are captured, modes of action and emotional states are perceived, which can be "triangulated" with the interview. At the same time, both methods will enable a more comprehensive study of the subject of the case.

Using the empirical method of scientific observation, an observation guide was developed to explore the subject's behavior, emotional responses, social interactions, and physiological reactions. This guide assessed attention, motivation, and cooperation while applying psychological techniques.

Observation provides insight into individuals' social and personal lives, allowing researchers to interpret emotions, infer meaning, and evaluate reliability by comparing verbal expressions with actions (Gómez, 2020; López, 2017). From an ethnographic psychology perspective, observation uncovers overlooked aspects of daily life (Ruiz, 2021), making it essential for a detailed and contextualized subject analysis.

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, the study followed behavioral guidelines proposed by Eysenck and Eysenck (1985) and Costa and McCrae (1992), creating a structured framework for observing and interpreting the subject's responses.

After detailing each category and subcategory proposed for the application and development of direct observation of the subject under study, the behavior and externalized emotions were exceptionally detailed. The social interactions of said subjects and their physiological responses were observed.

Thanks to this observation, it has been possible to observe behavior patterns that could be symptoms of anxiety, such as biting one's nails repeatedly and looking around restlessly as if searching for something.

Besides being restless and lost, her eyes were sad and tearful, reflected by her verbal behavior when referring to past events that greatly affected her. She seemed somewhat uncomfortable since the subject has a tendency to repeatedly think about adverse events (rumination), which, when externalized, allows him to be more aware of them and to get out of his comfort zone to release those stress patterns that cause him to think about such harmful acts; However, she cooperated and answered clearly and argued each of the questions asked; anxiety continually betrayed her. Meanwhile, the duration of negative emotions persists around the objects of conversation, always externalizing aversive behaviors and anguish about the issues that afflict her.

Hypothesis: The externalized behavior of the subject is a key point to manifest at first glance if he suffers from some anxiety or depression, which would make his affective-emotional stability difficult.

By creating an "interview guide," the behaviors and emotions of the subject under study could be explored from the welcoming and safe environment the evaluators provided. That is to say, the "interview" will provide a set of data that makes it possible to compare with other data obtained in the tests and subsequent techniques. When interviewing the subject, the evaluators must take into account how much the subject may or may not be affected, so they must be assertive

and provide feedback; therefore, the evaluators must not reveal a distance nor show signs of total coldness; they must, above all, know how to listen and not judge.

Therefore, Gómez (2019) states, “Through the interview, the psychologist can establish a relationship of trust that facilitates the patient’s openness” (p. 78). In this sense, the interview was developed to observe and analyze behavior and emotions in a controlled environment to understand the emotional state of the subject under study.

Through the “interview”, it was possible to gather personal and relevant information about the subject under study. At first glance and according to what the subject expressed, her most significant need is within the needs of belonging (affection) and esteem (respect from others towards her, showing low patterns of self-esteem (self-assessment, sense of self-esteem) and trust in others and the subject herself), since she wishes with all her might to meet her mother again and feel her love close by again (ability to restructure the field of action in the face of separation from the mother). In addition to making peace with her son (motive) and recovering the trust and the relationship of affection-parental attachment that they had (needs), she corroborates it with the phrase “strange as he was before”.

Here, the subject lets us see that everything negative that happens to him is caused by external factors and by the influence of other people; he says he feels “misunderstood” and does not tolerate being proven wrong. This shows his perception of the causes of the events in his life. His external locus of control shows that the individual is aware of the possibility of influencing his actions but does not take responsibility for the consequences. Instead, he attributes that responsibility to factors beyond his control.

At times, he has resorted to relieving his sorrows with God (world view) from that source of spiritual affection, which he says he seeks in himself and with his friends and family. At other times, he has wanted to isolate himself and try to reflect on himself from the solitude of his home, which depresses and irritates him simultaneously since he categorically states that he cannot find answers to many of his questions.

Hypothesis: An unresolved conflict can mean incredible frustration, leaving emotional scars that hinder the subject’s performance and affect his or her emotional and behavioral well-being.

The “10 Wishes Technique” instrument is a projective technique used to assess personality about the personal development of subjects, as it allows them to reflect on their aspirations, interests, and desires and reveal their ideal goals and purposes. Therefore, this technique is based on subjects being able to identify and prioritize their deepest desires, all of which allows the psychologist to obtain with greater clarity a series of data about what the subject being studied really values or not; given that, when the subject places a desire in

the foreground, that is, prioritizes it, he is giving it a specific socio-moral value, which can positively influence motivation and emotional well-being. For Schwartz (2012), this technique allows for “self-knowledge” because it encourages “introspection, allowing people to explore their desires and needs ... and a better understanding of oneself” (p. 45). Therefore, when the subject knows himself, what he wants, and his potential and limitations, he can better insert himself into the system of relationships in his environment.

As can be seen, the subject of study externalizes in his answers a very logical perception and, above all, very in tune with the social moment in which we live, plagued by materiality, irresponsibility, emotional deficiencies, and even material ones, even (without denying them outright). For a better understanding of the answers expressed in this technique, we will proceed to organize the expressed desires according to the areas of phonological integration, such as family, personal, social, community (socio-family, socio-community from the conception of this study), seen in their socio-psychological integration, because the subject actively relates to his environment. All this is to understand the guiding tendencies of the personality better, according to the areas of integration of this configuration from the hierarchies made by the subject, taking into account their interests, needs, and motives.

As can be estimated, this organization of desires by area has made it possible to understand how they work or how the subject reflects on the hierarchical order. In this case, the subject has five desires specifically (in items-desires 1, 2, 3, 4 and 8), the “family area” is weighted, leading to an understanding of how the subject is involved and values the family as a unit or fundamental cell of society (it has already been seen in the previous tests how the family plays an essential role for the subject, although it expresses the problems that have been seen, such as arguments, illness, distance, etc.), leaving him in stages of depression and anxiety. The family unites because it is the social axis of healthy interactions, which the subject needs from the understanding that he demands (as has been appreciated in other tests previously applied and evaluated).

In turn, it is observed that there is unity between society and the community, which affects the family area. It can be seen, then, how (in items-desires 6, 7, 9, and 10) such unity is evident from the integrative dynamics of “socio-family and/or socio-community” and “social”, properly speaking.

The subject under study shows in his answers a fairly adequate perception of what has already been analyzed: his problems regarding intra-family communication (subject-son) and with his mother (the grandmother). This gives rise to the fact that (in item-desire 5) the subject expresses that she wants to be understood (estimation of the reason because she believes she is always right), an issue that has also been revealed in the previous tests.

Hypothesis (10 wishes technique): The wishes and aspirations of the subjects under study depend on their motivations and life circumstances.

The “Sentence Completion Test (Rotter)” instrument is a projective technique used to assess the personality and emotional processes experienced by a subject. This test has allowed evaluators to obtain information about the attitudes, beliefs, and states in the sentimental component of personality through the presentation of incomplete sentences, from which the subject under study was able to project his experiences and ways of understanding his environment.

The subject reveals the needs, motives, and emotions that define her personality—reserved, introverted, and selective about what contributes to her well-being. She seeks affection but fears it, displaying mixed emotions. Loneliness serves as an escape (items 27, 29), yet she also shows deep attachment to her mother (items 11, 20, 21) and fears rejection from her son (item 13).

She frequently reflects on humanity, peace, health, and her family’s well-being (items 20, 34, 45) and feels she has failed as a mother and wife (items 20, 21), contributing to her isolation. She also values human and animal life (item 1).

To cope, she turns to God as a source of spiritual strength (items 8, 24, 25). She firmly rejects ingratitude and rejection, particularly from her son (items 13, 33, 31), and expresses disdain for selfishness and hypocrisy (items 10, 31), reinforcing her aversion to betrayal.

The subject appears dejected yet sincere in rejecting negative human behaviors such as ingratitude, contempt, and betrayal (item 33). She expresses frustration over these actions and perceives herself as misunderstood and judged, particularly as a woman (items 5, 12, 40, 41). This distrust stems from hypocrisy and pretense, making her need to organize her surroundings and correct others (items 6, 10, 19, 44).

Despite this, she also expresses solidarity and a desire to help others (item 48), showing a balance between disillusionment and a moral drive for improvement.

Hypothesis: This technique helps identify key personality traits, including self-esteem, interpersonal perceptions, and the presence or absence of conflicts.

The “HTP Test (House, Tree, Person)” instrument is another of the projective tests used to evaluate personality in order to know the emotional functioning of a subject through what they draw; therefore, when they draw a house, a tree, and a person, the subject externalizes their emotional expression and their interpersonal relationships, through how they perceive their relational environment.

Therefore, its importance lies in revealing unconscious aspects of the psyche through how the subject can assess his interpersonal relationships and perception of his environment (Koppitz, 1984; Cohen, 1993). Based on how the

house, the tree, and the person are drawn, it should be noted that the subject can reflect the perception of this person on his socio-family environment. For the evaluation of this test, it is necessary to take into consideration functional indicators that have been proposed by different psychologists in their studies and that have been adapted and applied to this case study. To this end, the aforementioned theoretical contributions and criteria of (Koppitz, 1984; Cohen, 1993) have been taken into account, as well as they have been intertwined and/or related to those proposed by (Martínez, 2020), taking their dimensions from them to provide an adequate integration of the methodological analysis in the qualification.

The indicators used to measure the HTP (House, Tree, Person) drawings, according to Koppitz (1984), Cohen (1993) and López (2005) are applied to the subject of the specific study as follows: The size of the drawings reflects the individual’s self-esteem and perception of themselves and their environment. The drawings’ level of detail and complexity can indicate the subject’s attention to detail and observational abilities. Symmetry within the drawings is linked to emotional stability, while proportions may reveal the individual’s sense of their place in the world. Color provides insight into emotional states and attitudes towards oneself and others. Omitted elements, such as missing windows on a house or branches on a tree, may signify aspects of emotional or social life that the subject avoids, denies, or represses. Finally, the interaction between the figures within the drawing offers clues about the subject’s interpersonal relationships.

The proposal of dimensions and indicators to measure the drawing of the Human Figure Test (HTP), as outlined by Martínez (2020), is applied to the specific subject of study in the following way. Dimension 1, Emotional, is assessed through indicators such as the expression of emotions, the representation of figures, and the use of colors in the drawing. Dimension 2, Relational, focuses on the size and position of figures and the interaction between elements within the composition. Dimension 3, Cognitive, evaluates the complexity of the drawings, attention to detail, and the spatial organization of the elements depicted. Lastly, Dimension 4, Self-image, considers indicators like the representation of the human figure, the proportions of the figure, and the inclusion of physical characteristics, all of which provide insight into how the subject perceives their own body and self. Figure 1 presents the drawings made by the subject of the study.

From this perspective, the following can be inferred: the subject may exhibit low self-image and self-concept, as inferred from how she paints the “man” as afflicted and dejected, with no symmetry or proportion. This suggests low emotional stability within her family environment. The subject may also struggle with emotional regulation, as reflected in her drawing of the “tree”. It symbolizes how she faces reality and grows as a social being, yet it depicts instability and in-

security. The absence of fruits, soil, or a stable base suggests socio-emotional vulnerability, which affects core personality functions such as needs, interests, motives, and values.

The subject may exhibit limited and fragile interpersonal relationships, as indicated by how she draws the house, reflecting a low perception of family dynamics. She appears dissatisfied and emotionally affected, grieving for her mother and son. The distant family relationships she mentioned in previous tests are also projected in this drawing, reinforcing her sense of affliction and discontent. The overall drawing suggests that her emotional struggles are linked to family instability, affecting her perceptions of reality. Her artwork reveals a devalued self-image, with signs of anxiety, depression, and irritability, which contribute to recurring misunderstandings with others.

In the HTP Test, the hypothesis posits that the house reflects the subject’s perception of family relationships and satisfaction with home life, the person represents self-perception self-esteem, and how the subject identifies with others, and the tree symbolizes personal growth, evolution, and goal achievement.

The “Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory Test” is a psychological test designed to measure, evaluate, and/or intervene to understand self-esteem, conceived as a psychological formation of a motivational type. This inventory was designed by the psychologist Stanley Coopersmith. Coopersmith himself (1967) expressed in this regard that “self-esteem refers to the evaluation that a person makes of himself, and the Self-Esteem Inventory is a tool that allows this evaluation to be measured objectively” (p. 12). Thus, the subject studied in this test could refer to how he perceives himself, believes his “self” is, and what feelings, perceptions, and motives guide his behavioral action. For Branden (1994), “self-esteem is the experience of being competent to face the challenges of life and being worthy of happiness” (p. 4).

For this evaluation, some indicators proposed by Stanley Coopersmith himself (1967) are used to obtain a general and organized idea of the subject’s personality, and the responses given to the test can be analyzed better with a specific structuring character.

Stanley Coopersmith’s indicators for studying self-esteem, as applied to the specific subject, include several key dimensions. Self-acceptance is assessed by determining how the individual feels content with themselves and embraces their strengths and limitations. Self-efficacy involves evaluating the subject’s confidence in accomplishing tasks and overcoming challenges. The quality of interpersonal relationships is examined through the individual’s perceptions of social support and acceptance. Additionally, the perception of success is measured by how the subject evaluates their achievements and failures and how these assessments impact their self-esteem. The tendency to engage in social comparison and the effects of these comparisons on self-image are also considered. Furthermore, attitudes toward the future are analyzed by looking at the subject’s expectations and perceptions of available opportunities and possibilities. Lastly, the influence of positive and negative emotions on self-esteem is considered.

The subject’s responses indicate a moderately optimistic self-perception, with an average self-esteem score of 17 points (3 “Yes” and 14 “No”). While he accepts himself, his self-esteem is asymmetric, balancing apparent confidence with underlying doubts. Although he claims that problems affect him minimally and that he has no difficulty speaking in public, inconsistencies in his responses suggest a mix of introversion and extraversion, reflecting a stable yet evolving personality.

The test will be analyzed using Coopersmith’s seven indicators, grouping items based on weighted criteria. For self-acceptance, the subject experiences occasional dissatis-

Figure 1. Drawing made by the subject of study, with the analysis according to the details represented from the subject’s perceptions.

faction and self-doubt (as seen in item 12) but also recognizes his characteristics and limitations (item 15), with family-related stress potentially influencing his self-perception and a notable lack of self-confidence affecting his ability to trust others without constant validation. Regarding self-efficacy, he demonstrates a medium level—considering himself trustworthy (item 25) while describing his life as complicated (item 13), which suggests diminished confidence in managing tasks and challenges. In terms of interpersonal relationships, he seeks validation. He struggles to feel entirely accepted (items 6, 8, 9, 12, 13, and 14), as further evidenced by sentence completion exercises that reveal discomfort in social settings; additionally, a low perception of social support and family integration (items 6, 14, and 16) points to difficulties in feeling included within his family.

His perception of success is uneven: he feels comfortable at work (item 17) but not in his family life (item 20). Concerning social comparison, although he does not wish to be someone else (item 24), and this reinforces his self-acceptance (item 21), he continues to struggle with group integration, particularly within his family, often seeking constant validation and even describing himself as unattractive (item 18), though his self-perception remains subjective. His attitudes toward the future reveal gaps in his pursuit of healthier environments at the family level despite feeling relatively satisfied in his work setting. Finally, in the realm of emotions and feelings, the subject displays emotional variability by identifying as friendly yet admitting to quickly becoming angry at home (items 5 and 6), indicating that improved family dynamics could enhance his overall self-perception. Overall, his dissatisfaction appears to stem not from within himself but from how he is perceived at home and in social contexts, causing him to oscillate between distancing himself from reality and desiring to belong—a reflection of his fluctuating self-esteem.

Hypothesis (Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory Test): Individuals who actively pursue life goals and interpersonal growth develop more excellent emotional stability and intelligence, leading to higher self-esteem scores.

The Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ), developed by Hans Eysenck, measures three key personality dimensions: Extraversion-Intraversion, Neuroticism, and Psychoticism. In this case, it helped analyze how personality traits influence behavior.

Eysenck (1990a) defines personality as a stable set of characteristics reflected in behavior over time and across situations. This test provides insights into temperament and its role in the subject's performance. The personality is the dynamic integration of psychic processes that shape an individual's way of being. Pretrovski (1980) further emphasizes that personality is a unit where the subject acts with strengths and

weaknesses, shaped by active social participation.

As can be seen, the subject under study manifests in his responses a generalizable perception of his behaviors (from an extraversion-introversion profile to one of apparent neuroticism). Therefore, it is objective that this subject could be classified based on his personality traits through this questionnaire (EPQ). This study aims to assess the subject by identifying which personality dimensions—extraversion-introversion, neuroticism, and psychoticism—most accurately describe their behavior.

Therefore, before beginning to evaluate the personality of the subject under study, we will define, according to Hans Eysenck himself (1985, 1990a, 1990b, 1994), the three dimensions that he understands make up the structure of personality in order to form a possible pattern or profile of the subject.

According to Hans Eysenck, the personality dimensions applied to the psychological evaluation of the subject under study include Extraversion, Neuroticism, and Psychoticism. Extraversion refers to a person's tendency to be sociable, active, and to seek stimulation in the company of others; extroverted individuals typically exhibit high energy levels and enjoy social interaction, whereas introversion is associated with self-absorption. Neuroticism measures emotional stability, with high levels often linked to experiencing negative emotions such as anxiety, depression, and irritability, while low levels suggest a more emotionally stable disposition. Psychoticism is related to tendencies toward impulsivity, aggression, and antisocial behaviors, with higher scores indicating traits like disinhibition and a lack of empathy.

Analyzing the subject's personality dimensions—specifically extraversion-introversion, neuroticism, and psychoticism—reveals that she frequently exhibits extraverted tendencies, as evidenced by responses in items 1, 3, 4, 27, 29, 30, 34, and 36. Despite previous indications of loneliness, she actively seeks social interaction, enjoys going out, and values the support of encouraging friends. Her openness is further demonstrated in items 41 and 48, where she expresses a clear desire to work and engage with colleagues. However, there is also a noticeable reserved aspect in her behavior, likely influenced by depressive symptoms stemming from family issues, which may drive her apparent need to seek sociability as a counterbalance.

It should be noted that (in items 5, 48, 51, and 53), she would not feel bad if she were not surrounded by people “most of the time,” just as she likes to work alone. Logically, she does not like continuous hubbub or agitation. She generally likes tasks in which she can work in isolation and alone.

The analysis of neuroticism (items 35, 38) reveals a deep emotional profile, as the subject frequently experiences anxiety, worry, and guilt. Concerns about her children's well-be-

ing and her mother’s health are recurrent themes. She also expresses irritability (item 43) and feelings of being misunderstood, with repetitive thoughts contributing to signs of depression. Additionally, she perceives herself as unlucky (item 37), reinforcing her emotional distress.

In contrast, psychoticism traits are absent (items 40, 41, 44, 46). The subject does not display impulsivity, aggression, or a lack of empathy. She is friendly, avoids conflicts, thinks before acting, and dislikes daring or insolent behavior. This indicates a strong capacity for empathy, demonstrating respect, and appropriate social conduct.

Depression and anxiety are evident in the subject’s responses, influenced by her family situation. The Eysenck Personality Test suggests a phlegmatic temperament, as indicated by her score of 9 in extroversion and 11 in neuroticism, placing her in Quadrant III C. This temperament is characterized by calmness, emotional stability, passivity, caution, and self-control.

Although phlegmatic individuals are generally balanced and composed, they may develop neurotic symptoms—such as depression, anxiety, and irritability—when exposed to prolonged stress or trauma. The subject tends to negative emotions in response to family difficulties, highlighting the impact of high-pressure environments. Research supports that even emotionally stable individuals can manifest anxiety and stress under extreme conditions (Eysenck, 1990; Goleman, 1995).

Figure 2 explaining personality patterns according to the Eysenck personality test. This test also provides insights into the subject’s locus of control (internal and external), which

influences how they handle challenges affecting their emotional well-being. Understanding this aspect was essential for enhancing self-esteem and resilience, allowing the subject to face personal and social life more effectively.

As Weiner (1985) stated, locus of control plays a key role in interpreting success and failure. The subject tended to downplay achievements and focus on failures, highlighting understandings. To improve adaptability, resilience must be strengthened, as locus of control is linked to self-efficacy and better stress management (Bandura, 1997).

Hypothesis (Eysenck Personality Test): High neuroticism increases vulnerability to anxiety and depression. Stressful family situations can trigger neurotic traits, leading to emotional distress, even in individuals with a predominantly phlegmatic temperament.

Conclusions

This study provided a detailed exploration of the subject’s personality, analyzing primary psychological units and motivational formations through various techniques and psychological tests (observation, interview, the 10 Wishes Test, Roter, HTP, Coopersmith, and Eysenck). The results accurately reflected the factors affecting the subject, offering key insights for evaluation and characterization from a clinical psychology perspective. The analysis enabled an understanding of the subject’s thoughts, emotions, and behaviors, identifying personality patterns between extraversion/introversion and neuroticism while ruling out psychotic traits. This precision was crucial for appropriate diagnosis and intervention. Furthermore, the study facilitated the subjects’ placement

Figure 2. Quadrant explaining personality patterns according to the Eysenck personality test.

within their social, family, and community context, recognizing these environments as essential support networks and protective factors in their socio-psychological development. Additionally, the subjects could reflect on themselves, externalizing emotional experiences and strengthening resilience, contributing to self-awareness, personal growth, and a sense of fulfillment.

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The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

Mercedes C. Jiménez and Israel Acosta: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, supervision, validation, visualization, drafting the original manuscript and writing, review, and editing.

Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable

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Statement on the use of AI

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